

Towards a common data model for semantic annotation of digital media: A new FOSS toolchain

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Abstract

Traditionally, the development of metadata standards and collection management systems has focused on the management of the separations between analog objects, their descriptive surrogates and the creation of finding aids (Hurley 2005). But born-digital artifacts, such as various media files and software applications, and their associated metadata records are created, managed, and used in the same environment. Describing the ever-expanding range of significant properties of these artifacts (Laurenson 2014), tracking data provenance (Rossenova et al. 2019), and allowing collaborative research and annotation can prove particularly challenging to traditional relational database systems and their information architecture models (Hurley 2005; Wiedemann 2019), which separate schema from content, depend on fixed vocabularies and categorizations, and tend to remain siloed and closed off

to external audiences. In the field of cultural heritage and the digital humanities, 2D- and 3D-digital representations of cultural assets are particularly heterogeneous in formats and structure (Blümel / Wessel 2019), hence standardized access and visualisation tools fail to meet new research objectives and institutional requirements. To bridge the gaps across traditional data management tools and media-rendering environments, at TIB's Open Science Lab we have developed a suite of tools as part of a larger national effort which involves the partnership between several research, library and cultural institutions (Altenhöner et al. 2020). In this poster we present our current development of an integrated FOSS (Free and Open Source Software) toolchain (Rossenova et al. 2022) that consists of three main components: 1) OpenRefine – for data reconciliation and batch upload (Stern 2019); 2) Wikibase – for linked open data storage (Alípio et al. 2019); and 3) Kompakt – for rendering and annotating 3D models, and other 2D and AV media files (Eide et al. 2019). All components of the toolchain feature graphical user interfaces aiming to lower the barrier of participation in the semantic web for a wide range of practitioners and researchers. The toolchain is envisioned as a collaborative environment with different levels of read/write access, wherein groups of researchers can work collaboratively on data upload and annotation with clear data provenance. In addition, we have placed particular emphasis on an open, community-oriented and agile development process.

Our toolchain follows FAIR principles, and adopts common standards like PIDs and the W3C annotation model, but the integration of the tools also depends on the application of a common data model that needs to accommodate a range of knowledge domains involved in the study of cultural heritage objects. This model facilitates linking media objects and annotations, and their cultural context (including historical people and places, geo-location and digital-capture-technology metadata), to the broader semantic web and various national and international authority records (GND, Getty's AAT, VIAF and more). The poster presentation will focus on the development of the common data model and how it aims to improve interoperability between datasets of digitised cultural objects. The presentation will be of interest to DH researchers, librarians and digital curators who manage research datasets containing diverse media files, and want to learn more about the possibilities of linked open data, open source software and collaborative annotation workflows.

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